

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

Report on the results of consultations with government ministries and funding agencies

Deliverable 4.3

26 November 2024 / Version 1.0

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

This work was funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101094690 (EuroGO-SHIP) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10051458, 10068242, 10068528]. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

About this document

Title	D4.3 Report on the results of consultations government ministries and funding agencies
Work Package	WP4, Science Inputs & Stakeholder Engagement
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Due Date	30.11.2024, M24
Submission Date	26.11.2024
Version	1.0

Dissemination Level

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<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

EuroGO-SHIP: Developing a Research Infrastructure Concept to Support European Hydrography is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon Europe Work programme topics addressed: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-DEV-01-01– Research infrastructure concept development. Start date: 01 December 2022. End date: 30 November 2025.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Task description	7
2. Process description	7
3. Results	9
3.1. Which organisations do hydrography (19).....	9
3.2. Where, how often (16).....	10
3.3. What gets measured (17)	12
3.4. Where does the data go (17)	13
3.5. Why (16)	14
3.6. Who pays (16)	14
3.7. How far in advance do you plan things (16)	15
3.8. Who decides about entering RIs (14).....	15
4. Learning points, actions and next steps	16
5. Glossary	17
6. Appendix Part 1. National contributions.....	18
7. Appendix Part 2. Slides from Introductory Webinars	32

Executive Summary

EuroGO-SHIP aims to produce a blueprint for a new research infrastructure to support European hydrography that is consistent with practitioner and end user needs, the existing Research Infrastructure (RI) landscape and funding agencies. This report details interactions we have had with key intergovernmental structures and practitioners (as proxies for funding agencies) to understand their views around the importance of hydrography, the basic programmes they support and the way in which decisions around RI membership in individual countries are made.

Ship-based hydrography is recognised by key intergovernmental structures (GOOS) and policy agencies (European Marine Board) as a fundamental component of the landscape, and thus an observing system that merits inclusion within the RI landscape. A more detailed analysis, conducted via a strategic dialogue with project partners and collaborators suggests that European hydrography is conducted via a diverse set of actors, delivering both research and policy-relevant information supported by both research and government funding. Programmes by individual countries frequently overlap and there are the beginnings of joint programming actions occurring to minimise costs.

Ocean data is archived predominantly in National Data Centres (NDCs) with pan-European and wider structures figuring at lower, but still significant, levels in the data landscape. Greater cooperation between countries has the potential to reduce costs and improve coverage, and is a likely activity that EuroGO-SHIP can support. The gateway to RI membership varies across countries, but what is clear is that in nearly every country the construction of a business case for that country to join EuroGO-SHIP needs to be undertaken by that country based on a blue print provided by EuroGO-SHIP. The next steps in this workstream will be to work with countries to gain more specific information around key decision makers in individual countries and to convene cross-project discussions on how best to engage with these actors over the 2025/6 period. In addition, we suggest a series of actions that EuroGO-SHIP can undertake now to help hydrographic communities be in a position to most easily produce a business case for membership later in this project or within a follow-on project. These are:

1. EuroGO-SHIP should help hydrographers identify the main relevant organisations in every country and where possible a national hydrographic committee that identifies and represents national scale priorities, to pave the way for joining a RI.
2. EuroGO-SHIP should aim to facilitate nations sharing information around their hydrographic programmes where appropriate to maximise the potential for cost savings and information return.
3. EuroGO-SHIP should identify key data pathways required to serve key customers and facilitate data following that pathway through training and best practice.
4. EuroGO-SHIP should support further work to understand the complex relationship between research and operational funding and activity in individual countries in support of designing its work programme

5. EuroGO-SHIP should support countries in exploring joint planning activities to maximise the return on the collective investment, where there are shared planning cycles.
6. EuroGO-SHIP should support individual scientists in individual nations in the work of building a business for their country to join.

1. Task description

EuroGO-SHIP aims to produce a ‘blueprint’ for a future RI that supports European hydrography and dovetails well with the existing RI landscape, but which also sits well with the funding agencies and institutions who will ultimately fund, deliver and benefit from the structure. This activity addresses this latter part by seeking to understand the existing international structures that these activities operate in, the scale of these activities and the decision-making structure that operates around nations entering RIs. To deliver this understanding we engaged in a discussion with JPI Oceans, the EuroGOOS operations committee and with individuals/organisations across the European community involved in delivering hydrography. Together these activities have enabled us to build a strong understanding of the value that funding agencies place on hydrography, the structure of hydrographic activities within European countries and the ways in which decisions related to entering RIs are made.

2. Process description

Consultation with Funding agencies and European ocean Observers. Funding agencies for ocean science within Europe are heterogeneous, however a common feature is that most ‘Ocean Research Active’ countries are members of either EOOS (European Ocean Observing System) or JPI (Joint programming initiative) Oceans or both. EOOS has the vision of ‘a European Ocean Observing System that is sustained and meets the specific needs of users’ with an associated mission ‘to coordinate and integrate European communities and organisations operating, supporting and maintaining ocean observing infrastructures and activities, fostering collaboration and innovation’. Its key forum is the operations committee which brings together ocean observers from multiple networks and funders from across the community. JPI Oceans is a forum where multiple research funding organisations come together to agree on shared priorities. The particular forum that we spoke at is known as the EOOS operations committee which brings together observers and funders to discuss key operational issues. We presented at their meeting convened jointly with JPI oceans and took questions. The two key features of the interaction were extremely strong statements in support of the value of ship-based hydrography by Emma Heslop who is a Programme Specialist at the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and Sheila Heymans who is the leader of the European marine Board, responsible for the multiple scoping activities that the marine Board undertakes on behalf of member states and other European Nations. We regard the strong endorsement of ship-based hydrography from these two organisations as being particularly significant.

We built on this direct interaction with EOOS, JPI Oceans, GOOS and the European Marine Board by contacting representatives of the hydrographic community across Europe in order to build a set of what we termed ‘pen pictures’ describing how hydrography is organised, funded and operated across Europe, with a particular focus on how decisions about joining

RIs are made and who the key people within each country are. We began this by developing a slide set (see appendix) with simple questions (to avoid survey fatigue) and then trialled it on EuroGO-SHIP investigators, including two webinars that served as a briefing session.

We then expanded our set of investigators to include multiple other European countries and their various representatives, nearly all of whom responded. We conducted four 1-h webinars to explain the context, concept and content of the Pen Pictures in more detail, to share results from existing pen pictures and to capture community feedback (see appendix for webinar slides). The discussions and feedback from these sessions are also included in our analysis below.

We extracted the basic replies to each question from each ppt set received and tabulated these in section 3). A full set of returns is shown in the appendix. Replies were provided in various forms: as narratives or bullet points, from personal or institutional perspectives, purely descriptive or with figures and maps. When analysing the data we had to interpret the results and make choices, for example as to how to group or categorize the responses. This is described below when appropriate.

Participants from outside EuroGO-SHIP consortium	
Black Sea workshop	Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Turkey, Georgia (no attendance but provided a presentation)
Webinar 1	Greenland
Webinar 2	Faroe Islands
Webinar 3	Croatia, Greece, Iceland, Portugal, Romania, Sweden, Turkey
Webinar 4	Belgium, Finland, Netherlands, Romania, Sweden

Table 1: Webinars and participating countries

3. Results

In addition to the eight countries represented in EuroGO-SHIP, we received pen pictures from nine countries and partial information through e-mail or workshop presentations from five more countries (Figure 1) outside the consortium.

Figure 1: Map of Europe showing EuroGO-SHIP countries (dark blue), countries outside the consortium that provided pen pictures (light blue), and countries that have provided feedback through webinar attendance or e-mail correspondence but no complete pen picture

Overall, we obtained information from >80% of maritime European countries. Notably, the Baltic states Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia are missing, as well as Albania, Slovenia and Montenegro. We plan to continue engagement with these countries through 2025 to obtain a more comprehensive overview of European hydrography. One very obvious feature of the data collected is that every country is different and that in many of them there is a wide variety of actors conducting hydrographic observations, thus the pen pictures represent only a partial snapshot of total activity. In many cases we received suggestions of relevant people to contact and will continue including them towards a more complete picture of national and international hydrographic observers. Not every country provided answers to each question. In the sections below the number in brackets in each subtitle represents the total number of answers we received to that particular question.

3.1. Which organisations do hydrography (19)

Figure 2 shows a frequency distribution of the sorts of institutions named by countries as undertaking hydrographic observations. In many countries there are multiple organisations carrying out hydrographic observations. The dominant sector, named by every country, is the research institute sector, with universities being the next most common (approximately 60%

of countries including over 10 in some countries such as France) with government agencies being named by only ca 40% of countries. Governmental agencies are related to fisheries and agriculture and include hydrographic offices. It is often unclear whether the latter conduct hydrographic observations or whether their activities are related to mapping coastal waters. Fisheries were explicitly mentioned twice as institutions (Germany) as well as governmental labs (UK).

Figure 2: Graph illustrating which sorts of institutions were named by individual countries in Europe. Y axis refers to number of countries naming a particular sector as being involved in delivering hydrography.

In almost every country there a very diverse set of actors (institutes, universities, governmental agencies) who appear to have limited interaction with each other, likely leading to inefficiencies. There are signs that the community in some countries is recognising this and addressing it: In Sweden, this has been addressed by forming a National Infrastructure that aligns Swedish research vessel and data infrastructures across government organisations to enhance access to vessels and equipment, technical expertise and quality-controlled data. In one further country we believe that this survey was the trigger for a broader scale dialogue between the relevant organisations which had not previously occurred. Our previous experience is that developing a national perspective is important for country level entry into a RI. This observation stimulates our first recommendation.

R1. EuroGO-SHIP should help hydrographers identify the main relevant organisations in every country and where possible a national hydrographic committee that identifies and represents national scale priorities, actions that will pave the way for joining a RI.

3.2. Where, how often (16)

All countries that addressed this question report that they carry out ship-based observations in their coastal zones and/or EEZ areas. Ten out of the 16 countries explicitly state operating at least one high-seas research vessel, including four countries operating an icebreaker. The high-seas research vessels operate mainly in the Northern Atlantic but occasionally also in the South Atlantic & Indian Oceans.

The frequency at which observations are obtained ranges from monthly over seasonal to multi-year observations (Figure 3), but most programmes appear to have annual activity. Contributions to international GO-SHIP activity form the bulk of the lower frequency programmes.

Figure 3: Graph showing the number of countries that report ongoing hydrographic programmes of set frequency

There is good geographical coverage in the Eastern mediterranean (Croatia and Greece). Romania and Bulgaria operate in the coastal and shelf waters of the Black Sea with one cruise per year beyond shelf waters (Romania). The Baltic Sea is covered by Sweden and Poland, as well as Finland (feedback during webinar). Individual nations run hydrographic programmes that are often partially overlapping in space. As an example, we have used the information around the spatial coverage of cruises to create a composite indicating coverage in this region (Figure 4). There is an impressive observing programme with frequent overlaps suggesting that if the combined information from these could be assembled the potential for whole system analyses is large and also that the potential for cost savings is high. Feedback from the webinars indicate that the co-operative programming of research vessel operations to maximise the return on investment is already practiced by some nations in the Atlantic sector. This observation stimulates our second recommendation.

Figure 4: Composite of information supplied by EuroGO-SHIP partners around where research vessel sampling and hydrographic programmes occur in European coastal waters.

R2. EuroGO-SHIP should aim to facilitate nations sharing information around their hydrographic programmes where appropriate to maximise the potential for cost savings and information return.

3.3. What gets measured (17)

Figure 5 shows a word cloud and histogram illustrating which parameters are measured by hydrographic programmes in European countries. All countries who returned information measure “classical” hydrography, that is temperature and salinity throughout the water column (Figure 5) and 17 out of 18 countries measure oxygen. More than half of the polled countries obtain observations of nutrients, carbon, chlorophyll and/or plankton, pH and ocean current speed. Quantities that are observed less frequently and non-systematically include fluorescence, isotopes, pollutants and litter, trace elements, alkalinity and Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs). Overall, there is a solid background of regular observations to quantify anoxia, ocean acidification and eutrophication in European coastal waters. This analysis will inform the priorities for new services and access opportunities.

Figure 5: Histograms and word clouds showing which parameters are routinely (blue) and opportunistically (red) measured by European hydrographic programmes.

3.4. Where does the data go (17)

This section focuses on the destination of the data obtained by individual countries with Figure 6 showing storage locations mentioned by European countries.

Figure 6: Data storage locations mentioned by European countries in response to the query around where they store their data. The y axis represents the number of countries mentioning a particular location.

Approximately 60% (13/19) countries mentioned a national data centre, with a slightly smaller fraction an institutional data repository (which is often the same). Seadatanet (an RI style association of national data centres) is mentioned by approximately half of the countries with a similar fraction mentioning EMODnet though there is uncertainty about how the data reaches this European scale repository. Some countries state that there is no clear policy for data management or that it is not yet in place and data forwarding to international data bases happens on a voluntary basis. Global data activities such as CCHDO (a repository for International GO-SHIP data) and GLODAP (a data synthesis product that brings carbon and associated data together into a common quality-controlled framework) are mentioned by some countries indicating a connection to global data activities, however the numbers mentioning these are less than the number of European countries involved in International GO-SHIP.

Figure 7 shows how many data destinations are mentioned by different countries. It is clear that different nations engage with highly variable numbers of data activities, which runs the obvious risk of data loss, version control and duplicated efforts. This observation stimulates our third recommendation.

Figure 7: Map of Europe with colour coding showing the number of data activities mentioned

R3. EuroGO-SHIP should identify key data pathways required to serve key customers and facilitate data following that pathway through training and best practice.

3.5. Why (16)

Figure 8 shows the motivations mentioned by countries in their descriptions of why hydrographic observations are undertaken, presented as both a word cloud and a histogram. Some interpretation of the returns was required for this analysis with the distinction between monitoring and directives not being clearcut. Research, monitoring and directive-driven commitments are the main motivations for conducting hydrographic observations.

Figure 8: Word clouds and histogram representing the primary motivation for undertaking hydrographic observations in mentioned by countries. In the left panel the y-axis represents the number of countries that mentioned a particular motivation with the red part

A large part of monitoring is related to fisheries (e.g. fish stock assessments). Directive-driven observations are related to national (e.g. UK Marine Strategy) or international commitments related to the MSFD (mentioned by 7 countries), WFD (4 countries) and OSPAR convention (2 countries). Monitoring is largely related to key environmental parameters such as water mass properties, stratification, ecosystem status, biogeochemistry and ocean acidification. Additionally, long-term monitoring of hydrographic repeated transects are carried out and overlap with research programmes (e.g. RAPID).

3.6. Who pays (16)

Figure 9 illustrates the number of countries that identify a particular funding source as being important for supporting hydrographic observations.

National research foundations are the dominant supporter, playing a crucial role in financing hydrographic observations with Government and EU funding sources also being mentioned. This dominant role is consistent with the answer to the

Figure 9: Histogram illustrating number of countries that identify a particular funding source supporting hydrographic observations. Red bars represent answers specifically associated with fisheries.

ERICs and AISBLs apply with decisions for the latter being made at institute or even project level while the former must be approved by a ministry. The national research council is involved in the process in at least three countries (Germany, Netherlands, Sweden) but its role is unclear: it is most likely the funding body for entering an RI. In Sweden, the research council reviews applications and decides whether to fund the RI-membership. ESFRI delegates are involved in at least three countries (Ireland, Germany, Portugal).

In summary there are varying internal structures across the various countries which means that a one size fits all approach to preparing a business case for joining a new RI is unlikely to be successful. Instead, we suggest that the core project concentrates on building the proposed structure via its existing processes and separately supporting key investigators in particular countries in business case preparation. This observation stimulates our sixth recommendation.

R6. EuroGO-SHIP should support individual scientists in individual nations in the work of building a business for their country to join.

4. Learning points, actions and next steps

This activity has revealed that ship-based hydrography is recognised by key intergovernmental structures (GOOS) and policy agencies (European Marine Board) as being a fundamental component of the landscape, and thus in our view, an observing system that merits inclusion within the RI landscape. A more detailed analysis, conducted via a strategic dialogue with project partners and collaborators suggests that European hydrography is conducted via a diverse set of actors, delivering both research and policy-relevant information supported by both research and government funding. Programmes by individual countries frequently overlap and there are the beginnings of joint programming actions occurring to minimise costs. Data is archived predominantly in NDCs with pan European and wider structures figuring at a lower, but still significant, level in the data landscape. Greater cooperation between countries has the potential to reduce costs and improve coverage, and is a likely activity that EuroGO-SHIP can support. Prior to that we encourage countries to consider a series of actions at the country level to prepare the way for EuroGO-SHIP implementation. The next steps in this workstream will be to gain more specific information around key decision makers in individual countries and to convene cross-project discussions on how best to engage with these actors over the 2025/6 period.

5. Glossary

CFC – Chlorofluorocarbons

EOOS – European Ocean Observing System

ERIC – European Research Infrastructure Consortium

ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

EuroGOOS – European Global Ocean Observing System

GOOS – Global Ocean Observing System

JPI – Joint Programming Initiative

MSFD – Marine Strategy Framework Directive

NDC – National Data Centre

OSPAR convention - The Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic

RI – Research Infrastructure

WFD – Water Framework Directive

6. Appendix Part 1. National contributions

Country	Which organisations do hydrography
UK	Oceanography labs (NOC, PML, SAMS, BAS) Universities (Southampton, UEA, Liverpool, Exeter, Plymouth, many others...) Government Fisheries-Environment Labs (Cefas, Scottish Government Marine Directorate SGMD [SEPA ??], AFBINI)
Ireland	Marine Institute, Ireland (coastal and open ocean)
Norway	IMR, NPI, UiT, UiB, NORCE
Italy	CNR, OGS, SZN, ISPRA, ENEA, Universities (2-3) -- these are grouped under CONISMA a consortium of Marine Science Universities
France	CNRS , Ifremer , IRD , Universities (10+)
Spain	Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities: CSIC (Oceanographic vessels from FLOTA), PLOCAN, SOCIB and Universities. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (Fishing and oceanographic research vessels). Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge [MITECO] () Hidrography-IHM, Spanish Navy (Cartography)
Germany	Universities, Fishery institutions, hydrographic offices, navy
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Institute for Research and Development of Marine Geology and Geoecology – GeoEcoMar, National Institute for Marine Research and Development ‘ Grigore Antipa’ Maritime Hydrographic Directorate
Belgium	Main operational bodies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RBINS-OD Nature (Institute of Natural Sciences) VLIZ (Flanders Marine Institute) Flemish Hydrography (Agentschap MDK) Research bodies: ILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), University of Ghent, University of Liege, Vrije Universiteit Brussels (VUB), Universite Libre Bruxelles (ULB), University of Antwerp, KU Leuven,...
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries (www.izor.hr, cruises in the whole Adriatic Sea) Ruđer Bošković Institute (www.irb.hr, cruises in the northern Adriatic Sea) University of Dubrovnik, Institute for Marine and Coastal Research (https://www.imp-du.com/, cruises in the southern Adriatic Sea)
Greece	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR): governmental organization that performs multidisciplinary, basic, and applied marine research. HCMR has a fleet of two research vessels capable of doing hydrography: R/V AEGAE0 (61m in length) and R/V PHILIA (20m in length). Greek Universities (University of Athens, University of the Aegean) occasionally collaborate with HCMR in data collection.
Iceland	Regular hydrographic observations in Icelandic Waters are performed by the Marine and Freshwater Research Institute (Hafrannsóknastofnun, hafogvatn.is) which runs both regular oceanographic cruises as a national monitoring program and CTD observations on fisheries cruises.
Netherlands	This is first and foremost the NIOZ Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research. https://www.nioz.nl/en Also, Rijkswaterstaat, which is more government oriented, does some research/measurements. https://www.rijkswaterstaat.nl/en
Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IMWM - NRI (Institute of Meteorology and Water Management – National Research Institute) (acronym in Polish: IMGW-PIB) IO PAN (Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences)
Portugal	Hydrographic Institute (Instituto Hidrográfico): STATE LABORATORY integrated in the PORTUGUESE NAVY, with financial and administrative autonomy, strategic guidelines defined by the Minister of National Defence in articulation with the Minister of Science, Technology

	and Higher Education and with the Minister of the Sea; National responsibilities in the areas of Bathymetric Surveying/Cartography, Physical Oceanography, Marine Pollution
Sweden	<p>Research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stockholm University (Electra) • University of Gothenburg (Skagerak) • Swedish Polar Research Secretariat (Oden) <p>Governmental monitoring and mapping activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swedish Coast Guard (KBV 181) • Geological Survey of Sweden (SGU; Ocean Surveyor) • Swedish University of Agricultural Science (Svea) <p>SWERVE: Swedish National Infrastructure that aligns Swedish research vessel and data infrastructures across government organisations to enhance access to vessels and equipment, technical expertise and quality-controlled data.</p>
Ukraine	Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Center and Research Institutes
Bulgaria	Institute of Oceanology - BAS
Georgia	<p>Tbilisi State University</p> <p>Iliia State University (research boat St. Iliia)</p> <p>Batumi State University</p> <p>Batumi Maritime Academy</p> <p>State Hydrography Center (catamaran Gagra)</p> <p>Black Sea Flora and Fauna Educational Scientific Research Center</p>

Country	Where, how often
UK	<p>Research cruises, including International GO-SHIP contributions: Open ocean, mainly Atlantic (including Southern Ocean and Nordic Seas). Frequency variable but approx 1 – 5 –10 yearly. Three global class vessels, one is ice-strengthened: RRS Discovery, RRS James Cook, RRS Sir David Attenborough. Cruise plans for Discovery and James Cook are available here, extending 12 - 18 months into the future</p> <p>SGMD: 3 surveys per year for hydrography on Scotia (in future may be fewer, funding & staffing constraints). Also, CTDs on fisheries cruises (lower data quality, fast descent!) typically cover half of North Sea in February and in August each year. Alba Na Mara (ecology and fisheries survey vessel, can measure 10-100 CTD profiles in a 3-week cruise). For both vessels, routes/coverage very similar for year to year</p> <p>AFBINI: CTD surveys 1 – 2 x per year for the Malin Shelf lines; up to 6 x per year for ‘grid’ of stations’ in UK waters to the east of NI, plus extension to the east to sample next to moorings LB06 and Cefas Liverpool Bay. Other stations include 2 x yearly Water Framework Directive winter nutrient survey CTDs within 1 km of shore, 20-30 stations all around the NI coast. Fisheries surveys do not run a standard CTD but tow a seabird CTD on the MIKNET (larval fish-catching net). Long term mooring at 38A (Irish Sea Buoy) has thermistor string, grab samplers and make BGC measurements;</p> <p>Cefas: [see map of 2018 survey track] RV Endeavour, example of year 2023, at sea for ~250 days (plus chartered to MoD ~ 50 d). Underway system (Ferrybox) used continuously for those 250 d. CTD rosette used during specific work only, estimate ~ 50 days (smartbuoy surveys 4 x yr, Clean Seas Environmental Monitoring Project, Celtic Sea/English Channel survey). Mini-CTDs (eg Valeport) or ESMX instruments attached to fishing and plankton gear during most (all?) cruises when CTD rosette is not used. Some ad-hoc work occurs ‘in-year’ that can involve CTD rosette or towed CTD.</p>
Ireland	<p>Operational oceanography and standard sections (e.g. Annual repeat associate GO-SHIP line) primarily in the Irish EEZ (exclusive economic zone) ;</p> <p>Infrequent transatlantic cruises in the N Atlantic (e.g. A02 every decade) ;</p>

	<p>Research specific cruises: usually there is one annual research cruise allocated to an area outside the Irish EEZ (e.g. subarctic or to the south).</p> <p>How often? 24/7 operations ~550 days yearly</p> <p>Days @ Sea in 2023 : RV <i>Celtic Explorer</i>: 295 days RV <i>Tom Crean</i>: 256</p>
Norway	<p>IMR: Fixed sections off the coast of Norway up to 6x a year, some only rarely; Large ecosystem and fishery surveys (– usually once a year per region);</p> <p>NPI: Fixed sections across the Fram Strait Various surveys in the Arctic Ocean and Barents Sea SO (once every few years);</p> <p>UiB: Nordic Seas, process studies (Turbulence, mixing, water mass pathways) – A few times a year; A few times a year 75°N section (A29) – once every ~5 years – recently in collaboration with IMR; Fjords around Bergen (ca 2x a year);</p> <p>NORCE: Nordic Seas, process studies (water mass pathways) – Once every few years, in collaboration with UiB and intl partners; Repeat section across 75N (A29) – Once every few years (~5) – In collaboration with UiB;</p>
Italy	<p>Italy at present operates 2 high-seas ships (1 is an ice-breaker), i.e. Gaia Blu and Laura Bassi. Until 2023 CNR also used a small coastal ship, now there might be smaller coastal vessels, not sure about in number (a couple...). The fleet is mainly used by CNR and OGS, for RV Gaia Blu the new access rules are being rewritten, and intention is to make this ship available to non-CNR national users. Both CNR and OGS have a commission to evaluate the ship time proposals on an annual basis. Occasionally Laura Bassi contributed to polar GO-SHIP lines, we plan to cover 2 associated lines in the Mediterranean Sea (Med-SHIP) at 4-5 year intervals. There is no sustained national programme committed to make hydrographic measurements in the Mediterranean or in Italian waters.</p>
France	<p>The French Oceanographic Fleet operates 6 high-seas ships (no ice-breaker), 5 coastal ships and 7 station ships that run all year-round (with a lightened schedule in winter). Two multi-organism scientific committees to evaluate and rank the proposals (annual call) One GO-SHIP line (A25-OVIDE-BOCATS, biennial) and 2 potential associated lines (PIRATA, MOOSE, both annual)</p>
Spain	<p>The Spanish oceanographic fleet is operated under three different governmental entities:</p> <p>Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities operates the main oceanographic fleet, the one related to GO-SHIP lines (reoccupations of A25-OVIDE, A24N, A17, A10,...), link to FLOTA here;</p> <p>Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food operate the vessels with responsibilities on evaluation of fisheries, but they have also hydrographic capabilities. (Link here Fishing and oceanographic research vessels);</p> <p>Hydrography-IHM, Spanish Navy has responsibilities related to navigation, i.e. cartography, but their vessels have also hydrographic capabilities. A side note is needed for the oceanographic vessel A33-Hesperides which is owned and crewed by navy, but operated and funded by UTM-CSIC (Ministry of Science).</p> <p>Regional agencies (INTECMAR, AZTI,...)</p>
Germany	<p>All groups that do ocean marine observations acquire hydrography if it is needed. There is no general role that applies.</p>
Romania	<p>Black Sea Waters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> coastal and shelf waters by GeoEcoMar (once per year), NIMRD Grigore Antipa (twice per year), and MHD (twice per year);- beyond shelf waters (GeoEcoMar) - one cruise per year (generally in summer)
Belgium (map)	<p>RBINS – OD Nature: RV Belgica can operate in open ocean and in areas with limited sea ice cover; operating area includes the North Sea, the Northeast Atlantic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea, with an Ice class for summer operations in arctic areas and a 30 day autonomy.</p> <p>VLIZ: coastal waters; Main operational area is Belgian Coast and Southern Bight of North Sea. VLIZ is programme manager for RV Simon Stevin (owned by DAB VLOOT)</p> <p>MDK: Belgian Continental Shelf (SIRIUS) and the Western Scheldt (several small coastal vessels)</p>
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In coastal regions, monthly to seasonally, temporal and spatial coverage depends on the requirements of the project or monitoring obligations In open Adriatic regions, seasonally over few regular transects, annually as ancillary measurements to the fisheries sampling

Greece	Ship-based observations are carried out in both open sea and coastal waters of the Greek Seas, the Eastern Mediterranean (and occasionally in the Red Sea in collaboration with Saudi academic institutions). The rate of data collection in the Greek Seas is roughly twice per year.
Iceland	The hydrographic monitoring program is conducted on cruises with a station grid on 10 sections around Iceland, 3-4 times per year with the aim of making observations each season. Large ecosystem and pelagic fisheries cruises, often as a part of an international program, are done annually per region but have dynamic cruise design so the CTD stations do not have fixed positions in general.
Netherlands (map)	The NIOZ Pelagia is the only Dutch research vessel for the ocean (and will be replaced soon). The Pelagia is doing research about 70% of the time. Mostly in the Atlantic (North and South), but occasionally in Indian Ocean. (Figure showing research location since 2019.) The NIOZ also has two other ships that do more coastal water research. Note, it is all project based. So based on research proposals that obtain funding for projects. There are in principle no repeated sections or hydrography stations as part of a larger organisation or consortium. There is the case of a senior research scientist at NIOZ maintains a bunch of moorings as part of the OSNAP array for the last 10 years. Mostly using the Pelagia and mostly funded through the Dutch system. But this is still proposal based and not secured.
Poland	IMWM - NRI : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polish EEZ • Regular monitoring from over 40 years • Six cruises per year (Feb/Mar, Apr, Jun, Aug, Sep, Nov) • 21 permanent stations • One high frequency station (12/year) – ZP6 IOPAN: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baltic Sea cruises occur approximately four times a year, excluding the summer months (July and August), with a focus on the southern Baltic Sea region. • West Spitsbergen Current (eastern part of the Fram Strait). More than 30-years long observations of CTD, water currents, heat transport etc. made along several latitudinal cross-sections. Recently this was supplemented with oxygen, nutrients, but also marine CO2 system (since 2019). • West Spitsbergen fjords - Hornsund, Kongsfjorden, Isfjorden. Ecological monitoring of ecosystem changes - CTD plus O2 collected as supportive parameters. • Cross-section between Gdansk Deep and Arkona Basin in the Baltic. CTD+O2. Conducted mainly to trace propagation of Major Baltic Inflows and stratification. • Coastal station in Gdansk Bay (the pier in Sopot) + mouth of Vistula River (southern Baltic). Sampled weekly since 2016 for CTD, O2, nutrients, carbon (organic and inorganic), chlorophyll
Portugal (map)	Multidisciplinary cruises (CTD profiling, Water Sampling,...) Portuguese Continental area: 1-2 cruises each year Azores and Madeira Archipelagos: 1 cruise each/year Cape Verde Archipelago: 1 cruise in 2021, open possibility for other cruises in near future. Regular cruises for bathymetric surveying in close collaboration with national authorities Angola, São Tomé and Príncipe, Guiné-Bissau: cruises for bathymetric surveying in close collaboration with national authorities. No hydrographic cruises in recent years Morocco margin: 1 cruise in 2009
Sweden (map)	Electra: Baltic Sea; many usually short voyages (max 11 days); Skagerak: Baltic Sea, North Sea; other areas (e.g. Iceland, Greenland, Svalbard) upon request; 7-10 expeditions per year; max 21 days; Oden: Arctic Ocean; one expedition per year; 4-6 weeks; KBV 181: Gulf of Bothnia; ca 10 expeditions per year; 11 days – 3 weeks; Ocean Surveyor: Swedish Economic Zone; number of expeditions per year varies; 1 week long; Svea: North Sea, Baltic sea; North Atlantic and polar regions is possible; 30-40 expeditions per year; max 16 days;

Country	What gets measured
UK	Research Cruises (GO-SHIP): CTD: T, S, DO. Bottle: Nutrients, carbon (DIC, Total Alk, soon pH), S, DO. Bottle sometimes: CFCs, stable isotopes (C, O, others). Research cruises (not GO-SHIP): CTD: T, S, DO as a minimum. Depending on the science, can include the GO-SHIP parameters too. SGMD: Scotia: T, S, DO, (Fluorescence, Turbidity). Plus bottle samples [12 Niskins on Hydrography cruises; single bottle on fisheries cruises have a single bottle normally (or take out of the ship's seawater flow system)]. Bottles

	<p>are analysed for nutrients (Total Oxidised Nitrogen, Phosphate, Silicate), carbonate chemistry (very limited), and dissolved oxygen.</p> <p>AFBINI: Corystes: T, S, DO, nutrients, optical backscatter, chlorophyll fluorimetry, pH (DIC added recently)</p> <p>Cefas: Endeavour: Rosette (SeaBird CTD with 12 x 10 litre niskin bottles): T, S, DO (bottles – nutrients, plus (it depends: contaminants, hydrocarbons, metals, eDNA)</p>
Ireland	BGC, physics, biology – oceanography [e.g. Ocean Climate cruise: Level 1 GO-SHIP parameters]
Norway	<p>Fixed sections: T, S, nutrients, zooplankton + oxygen, carbon chemistry;</p> <p>Large ecosystem and fishery surveys – T, ST, S, microstructure, O₂, nutrients, carbon chemistry, CFCs/SF₆, d¹³C</p>
Italy	<p>Mostly temperature, salinity, oxygen (SBE911, SBE43...), and currents (SADCP, LADCP);</p> <p>Almost systematic: nutrients and dissolved oxygen</p> <p>Non-systematic Carbonate system parameters, trace elements, isotopes; No Italian facilities or expertise for CFCs (one in University of Genova, but not sure about results)</p>
France	<p>Mostly temperature, salinity, oxygen (SBE911, SBE43...), and currents (SADCP, LADCP)</p> <p>Not systematic: nutrients, pH, alkalinity, trace elements, isotopes</p> <p>No French facilities or expertise for CFCs.</p>
Spain	<p>Mostly temperature, salinity, oxygen.</p> <p>Not systematic currents (SADCP, LADCP)</p> <p>Almost systematic: nutrients and dissolved oxygen</p> <p>Not systematic: MCS (pH, TALK, DIC), N₂O/CH₄, trace elements, isotopes</p> <p>No facilities or expertise for CFCs.</p> <p>Facilities and expertise for MCS and N₂O/CH₄</p>
Germany	All groups that do ocean marine observations acquire the parameters that are required for them/their purpose iow. no general rule applies. Most likely T is always acquired.
Romania	CTD parameters (temperatures, salinity, DO, fluorescence, pH, turbidity); DO (Winkler); Alkalinity; Nutrients (PO ₄ , SiO ₂ , NO ₃ , NO ₂ , NH ₄); Chlorophyll; TOC/TN
Belgium	<p>RBINS: T, S, surface pCO₂,... (UW); discrete samples from CTD casts</p> <p>VLIZ:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UW: T, S (Note that CTD and TSG sensors are not calibrated against samples and only using periodic cal from Seabird); Surface pCO₂ ; Surface Dissolved Oxygen Discrete samples from CTD casts: 1/month: TA, DIC, pH, Oxygen (winkler) (positions related to the VLIZ ICOS Station BE-FOS-Thornton Buoy https://meta.icos-cp.eu/resources/stations/OS_1199); 1/month: Various pigments, Phytoplankton Sampling (activities related to LifeWatch) <p>MDK: acoustic measurements (UW); CTD casts at discrete locations with Valeport sensors</p>
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature and salinity by CTD probes at all stations Nutrients and dissolved oxygen at many stations Primary production/chlorophyll, carbon, trace metals at selected stations Currents (at some cruises, by both shipborne and moored ADCPs) Some specific biogeochemical variables, marine litter and other during the monitoring for the EU Directives (Marine Strategy Framework Directive - MFSO, Water Framework Directive - WFD)
Greece	Most of the common Oceanic Variables are measured, i.e. T, S, oxygen, nutrients, inorganic/organic carbon, chlorophyll and less frequently isotopes and carbon system variables (alkalinity etc.)
Iceland	<p>On hydrographic monitoring cruises: T, S, O₂, PAR, Fluorescence with sensors on the CTD; discrete samples are taken for S and O₂ on every station for calibration of sensors and on selected stations for: ChlA, nutrients, TA and DIC.</p> <p>On fisheries cruises: T, S, fluorescence with the CTD; discrete samples for S, nutrients and chlorophyll.</p> <p>From 2024 both vessels underway system will be equipped with a pCO₂ system operated on every cruise.</p>
Netherlands	<p>Standard set up of the ships CTD is Conductivity (SBE4), Temp (SBE3), Pressure (SBE9), DO (SBE43), Transmissometer (C-star), Fluorometer (Aquatracka), PAR (SBE PAR-LOG), OBS (WetLabs), Altimeter (Valeport).</p> <p>Standard analyses that can be done on board (using Niskin) are: Ammonium, Nitrate, Nitrite, Phosphate and Silicate.</p> <p>Additional stuff (with extra support like a container with equipment or at NIOZ using samples from the Niskin) are: DIC, HS- TDP, DOC</p>

	Based on the project, additional things can be measured: this can include turbulence (VMP6000), nanoplastic, velocity and (much) more.
Poland	<p><u>IMWM-NRI:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water column: CTD, oxygen, pH, pCO₂, nutrients, chlorophyll a • Biological elements: zooplankton, phytoplankton, zoobenthos, benthic plants • Hazardous substances: heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants in fish, mussels, benthic plants, seawater, bottom sediments • Marine litter • Underwater noise <p>IO PAN:</p> <p>CTD, water currents, heat transports, more recently oxygen, nutrients, but also marine CO₂ system (West Spitsbergen current and fjords); CTD+O₂ (Baltic), CTD, O₂, nutrients, carbon (organic and inorganic), chlorophyll (southern Baltic)</p>
Portugal	<p><u>Parameters Measured by CTD probe</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressure, Temperature, Conductivity (Salinity) – all systems • Fluorometry, Nephelometry – depending on the system • Dissolved Oxygen, pH – depending on the system <p><u>Other Measurements Associated</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current profiles from LADCP in CTD frame • Current profiles from Vessel Mounted ADCPs • Marine Geology measurements (grabs, corers, seismic) • Multibeam <p><u>Water Sampling (Rosette samplers 12 bottles max 8 litres)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CTD in-situ calibration (analysis at IH Labs) • Nutrients (analysis at IH Labs) • Heavy Metals (analysis at IH Labs) • PAHs and OCPs (analysis at IH Labs) • Chlorophyll (analysis at IH Labs) • other biological in collaboration with other institutions <p><u>Ongoing pumping systems</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microplastics (analysis at IH Labs)
Sweden	<p>Ferrybox (except Ocean Surveyor): T, S, fluorescence, oxygen, pH, pCO₂;</p> <p>CTD: T, S, oxygen, fluorescence, turbidity, pCO₂, pH;</p> <p>All vessels have weather station platforms (at various stages of readiness from base platform with no sensors to fully operational system)</p>
Ukraine	<p>meteorological (atmospheric pressure, wind speed and direction, air temperature and humidity, type and amount of cloudiness, atmospheric phenomena, precipitation, visibility);</p> <p>— temperature and salinity of water on the surface of the sea, sea waves, currents, color and transparency of water, concentration of dissolved oxygen, pH value;</p> <p>— the distribution, thickness and drift of ice, the position of the edge of the ice and floating ice;</p> <p>— vertical distribution (on standard observation horizons) of oceanographic parameters - water temperature and salinity, speed and direction of currents, concentration of oxygen dissolved in water.</p>

Country	Where does the data go
UK	<p>Research vessels: RT CTD profiles (T, S) to WMO GTS and CMEMS; final versions of datasets to BODC, EmodNET-physic, SeaDataNet, WOD. For GO-SHIP cruises and some other research cruises, CTD and bottle data also go to CCHDO (at PI/CS discretion). Data pathways: we think BODC forwards data (or rather links to archived data) to SeaDataNet. Not sure about EmodNET and WOD, maybe WOD has to gather data from BODC from their index of CTD profiles (?).</p> <p>SGMD: RT CTD profiles (T, S) to WMO GTS and CMEMS; 'final' datasets to ICES & BODC (one annual submission in June, about 4 y behind at present but have plans in place to catch up). SGMD had assumed onwards fwding to WOD, SeaDATANet, Emodnet etc after they submit to BODC/ICES, but not the case (different for NERC researchers? Ask BODC)</p> <p>AFBINI: in-house database (aiming to ERDDAP), ICES (some but not all), Merman (UK db for mar monitoring data for Clean Seas programme, part of UK Marine Strategy – to OSPAR, ~6 stations), none to BODC (except Merman is hosted by BODC). Data is contributed to MCCIP process. Committed to changing the data process.</p> <p>Cefas: Cefas Data Portal (1989-), BODC, ICES</p>

Ireland	National database: All data is stored in the Irish National Oceanographic Data Centre, i.e., NODC (hosted by the Marine Institute) International databases CCHDO: GO-SHIP ICES: Fisheries, CTD and chemical data (e.g. CTD, nutrients, DO, DIC/TA) GLODAP and SDG 14.3.1 (e.g. DIC/TA) EMODnet (e.g. chemical, seabed/habitat mapping, CTD via SeaDataNet) Copernicus Marine Service <i>In Situ</i> Thematic Assembly Centre (e.g. tide gauges, databuoys etc.)
Norway	Norwegian Marine Data Centre, ICES, MERCATOR etc Norwegian Polar Data Centre, Norwegian Marine Data Centre ICES(?) etc Norwegian Marine Data Centre ☒ ICES ☒ NCEI/CCHDO, GLODAP
Italy	OGS to National Data Centre: https://www.ogs.it/en/national-oceanographic-data-centre-nodc CNR commitment to open data, but no clearly defined data flow yet Seadatanet (volunteer) Emodnet ingestion portal (volunteer)
France	NRT data: Coriolis National Data Centre (NDC): SISMER (now merged with ODATIS) Seadatanet (the NDC is part of the consortium so data are pushed automatically) Seano: by project, with doi (examples: Bocats2 2023 , PIRATA CTDs)
Spain	Seadatanet UTM Data Center Seano
Germany	Real time: those which send data in real time send that via the German Weather Service DWD to GTS or via Coriolis to GTS. Delayed mode: The data first goes into the repositories of the institutions and respective data managers send the data to further centres: ICES; Panagaea; German Oceanographic Data Centre at the BSH (DOD). Other rules may apply.
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Romanian Oceanographic Data Center (https://www.nodc.ro/), as well as other European databases (EMODNET, SeaDatnet) or project database (e.g. BRIDGE-BS) Maritime Hydrographic Directorate provided data only for the Ministry of Defence.
Belgium	VLIZ: Institute's data system (e.g. MIDAS, MDA); RI Data systems (LifeWatch, ICOS); EMODNet; SOCAT (UW CO2 data); MDK: At this point this is only used locally and for the determination of sound velocity profiles used in the acoustics of surveying. I have asked to log the data as a test now, and this could be implemented in the near future.
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National data centre and /or institutional databases Some data (but too few) goes to European databases (EEA, SeaDataNet)
Greece	Data are fed into the National Data Centre (https://hnodc.hcmr.gr/) as well as in other European data bases like Seadatanet, Emodnet, CMEMS, etc.
Iceland	There is no clear policy on where the data goes. All data goes to institutional database. The regular hydrographic cruise data goes to SDN, pelagic fisheries data goes to ICES. The Institute's database is in fact the national data centre.
Netherlands	The data is collected on the NIOZ Data Archive System (DAS): https://www.nioz.nl/en/research/dataportal/das
Poland	IMWM-NRI: Data is reported to the ICES database, HELCOM database, EMODNet IOPAN: Institutional Database
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional Database: At IH Data Centre - access to public provided through institutional website (work in progress) National Data Centre: Instituto Hidrografico and Instituto Portugues do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA, another Portuguese State Laboratory) are presently implementing the Portuguese National Oceanographic Data Centre (NODC-PT). Data Aggregators: Access to metadata and selected data from institutional website system (for general data, aggregators comprise EMODnet, SeaDataNet, Copernicus, GTS, HF radar European Node, ...)
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electra: Bolin Centre Database (?) Skagerak: not yet delivering data Oden: Swedish National Data Service (SND) KBV 181: not yet clear Ocean Surveyor: Kept in-house, most data has security classification levels and cannot be shared Svea: National archive for oceanographic data (SHARK), Database for Coastal Fish (KUL) (?) <p>SWERVE's objective is to ensure that Ferrybox, weather station and CTD data is delivered to SMHI and onwards to COPERNICUS and EMODnet in the coming years.</p>

	To the Ukrainian hydrometeorological center or to the organization that organizes the scientific research cruise
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Country	Why
UK	<p>Research Vessels: GO-SHIP repeat hydrography is for ocean and climate research; sustained observations cruises carry out CTDs alongside their ocean/climate/ecosystems research such as PAP, RAPID, OSNAP mooring trips; other 'blue-skies' cruises are for increasing scientific knowledge; RT data contributes to ocean and weather forecasting.</p> <p>SGMD: prevailing conditions monitoring for UK Marine Strategy ('UK Marine Strategy' (not MSFD!!)), environmental conditions as part of fish stock assessments; offshore wind consenting (background research for consenting process); support/conditions for Marine Protected Areas.</p> <p>AFBINI: Main driver is UK Marine Strategy. Also there is an ecosystem approach to marine environmental (was fisheries) management. Marine climate, detection of stratification (strength and timing), which is key to NI's main fishery. Clean Seas and Healthy & Biodiverse Seas group. Biology and Acoustics programmes are delivered off the back of these hydrographic platforms/measurements.</p> <p>Cefas: UK Marine Strategy, The Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (the 'OSPAR Convention'), Defra's priority outcomes (Fisheries Act 2020, Joint Fisheries Statement including Fisheries Management Plans, Marine and Coastal Access Act (MCAA), Conservation of Offshore Marine Habitats and Species Regulations 2017), ICES commitments.</p>
Ireland	<p>Legal: Directive driven, e.g. Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and Data Collection Framework (DCF), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Water Framework Directive (WFD)</p>
Norway	<p>Watermass properties/distribution heat content, for ocean reanalyses, primary production status, ecosystem and fisheries status, OA monitoring, argo++ deployment and calibration Watermass properties/distribution, sea ice, primary production status, ecosystem status, OA monitoring, mooring etc deployments and calibration Watermass properties/distribution/mixing/pathways, glider and mooring deployments;</p> <p>Contribution to international GO-SHIP;</p> <p>Fjord projects, student cruises ;</p>
Italy	<p>Mainly research (circulation, climate, acidification...),</p>
France	<p>Mainly research (circulation, climate, acidification...), but also water quality monitoring</p>
Spain	<p>Research (circulation, climate, acidification...) and water quality monitoring</p>
Germany	<p>Depending on the institutions it will be: Water Quality, MSFD compliance, ocean acidification, fisheries, research, monitoring, advice, climate observations</p>
Romania	<p>Most of the hydrographic data are used to fulfillment the compliances of the MSFD. In addition, some of the data are used in different national or European research projects</p>
Belgium	<p>VLIZ: Within the remit/contribution of the institute to ICOS and LifeWatch ERICS; research projects;</p> <p>MDK: Internal purposes, i.e. determination of sound velocity profiles used in the acoustics of surveying</p>

Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most cruises are done through requirements defined by EU Directive (MSFD, WFD) • Some cruises (at some repeated transects) are carried out as a part of institutional long-term monitoring activities • Some specific cruises are carried out within the research projects • One large cruise per year is carried out through the fisheries monitoring programme
Greece	Primary motivation is the fulfilment of monitoring obligations stemming from major programs like MSFD and WFD, and in general from all research programs that need in-situ data.
Iceland	The objective is to monitor key environmental parameters in Icelandic Waters including water mass properties, nutrients, carbonate chemistry, ocean acidification, primary and secondary production. Fisheries cruises have the objective of monitoring the status of ecosystems and fish stocks. The environmental data is in part used to fulfill Iceland's obligations for OA monitoring, WFD monitoring and Ospam monitoring.
Netherlands	<p>NIOZ performs fundamental research. The research done by the ships does mostly project based fundamental research. Rijkswaterstaat does some monitoring such as water quality monitoring, but this has different purposes. It is not in the open ocean, maybe in the North Sea.</p> <p>NIOZ is not obliged to do monitoring work for the North Sea. But they do do monitoring in the Wadden Sea with coastal vessels. Although this is mostly benthos and less hydrography.</p>
Poland	<p><u>IMWM-NRI</u>: monitoring in the Polish EEZ is a part of State Monitoring Program coordinated by Chief Inspectorate for Environmental Protection. The monitoring programme of Polish marine areas includes elements necessary to meet the requirements of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive and the results are the basis of marine environment status assessment. Poland closely and actively cooperates with Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) regarding the common approach to monitoring and assessing the condition of the Baltic Sea (by participation of experts from IMWM-NRI in experts groups).</p> <p><u>IO PAN</u>: statutory activities + research; ecological monitoring of ecosystem changes; trace propagation of Major Baltic Inflows and stratification</p>
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional programs for the monitoring and knowledge of environmental conditions in waters of national interest; • Studies developed in the framework of national and european research projects; • Support Portuguese Navy mission through knowledge of marine environment conditions (including operational support during response to crisis at sea); • Contracts for conducting studies of environmental conditions. • Some of the data collected is contributing to national commitments such as MSFD (D5, D8 and D11) or to regional conventions such as OSPAR (contaminants); • Some of the data collected is being shared and contributing to specific ICES working groups.
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electra & Skagerak: Research and Education • Oden: Research (1 voyage a year, otherwise the vessel is used by the Government for ice breaking) • KBV 181: Governmental monitoring with some research as piggy—back on the monitoring activities • Ocean Surveyor: Governmental monitoring/mapping • Svea: Governmental monitoring

Country	Who pays
UK	<p>Research Cruises incl GO-SHIP: funded via NERC (part of UKRI) reactive grants (~4 x per year) and also longer term projects, for example, CLASS ran 2018 – 2024 (https://projects.noc.ac.uk/class-project/) this will be replaced by Atlantis. National research funding is the primary source. Max timescale is 5 years.</p> <p>UK contributes to:</p> <p>JPI Oceans - Occasional funding through NERC/Defra;</p> <p>Horizon Europe - occasional funding through associate status of the UK;</p> <p>Small annual contributions to WMO/IOC OceanOPS, and to the EuroArgo ERIC (both using UK Govt Argo funding);</p> <p>SGMD: Scottish government pays, this is ongoing and considered to be “sustained”.</p> <p>AFBINI: DAERA (Department for Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs), enhanced with European and Defra grants.</p> <p>Cefas: Defra / or Defra-group organisations like EA, JNCC, etc. Sustained funding depends on spending reviews – routine surveys are ring-fenced – there is no ‘certainty’ but flat funding is usually forthcoming. Surveys are fitted/trimmed to suit available budgets.</p>
Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ship time for research is funded by the Marine Institute Policy, Innovation and Research Support (PIRS) • MSFD and WFD monitoring is funded by the Department of housing planning and local government

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU multi annual cycle funding: CFP is funded through the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine [Common Agricultural Policy and Common Fisheries Policy and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) Programme]
Norway	Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (mostly) + Climate and Env. Ministry, Norwegian Research Council, EU projects
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research grants from Italian Ministry of Research (via calls) European grants Ship-time is provided without fee for successful applications (and these funds are provided by the Ministry to CNR for Gaia Blu and to OGS for Laura Bassi)
France	<p>Ship cost is funded by the ministry via Ifremer.</p> <p>Research grants from CNRS, Ifremer, IRD (via calls) for the scientific work National Research Agency (ANR) for the science and marginally for the ship cost. European grants (marginally)</p>
Spain	<p>National Research Agency (AEI)</p> <p>Different grants</p> <p>Direct fundings</p>
Germany	Depending on the institutions and purpose of observations within: dedicated funding line for monitoring; short term research projects (DFG, BMBF, EU: typically 3 to 4 years); longer term and very broad research commitment (e.g. HGF programm oriented funding is now 6 years and funding is flexible to use; DAM Mission funding is 3 years with chance of renewal); ship applications run for a cruise and provide all support for observations to be carried out (no other project needed)
Romania	<p>National funding are provided by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization Ministry of National Defence Ministry of Environment, Water and Forests <p>EU research programs and private sectors provide funds as well.</p>
Belgium	<p>VLIZ: RV Simon Stevin operations are supported by the Flemish Government. Participation in ICOS & LifeWatch are funded by the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)</p> <p>MDK: Institutional budget</p>
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National budget, through MFSD and WFD monitoring budget National and EU budgets, through fisheries programmes Ad hoc research grants
Greece	Funding comes from European and national programs. National funding comes mostly from the ministry of environment and the ministry of development. Private funding also exists (e.g. fisheries)
Iceland	Funding is mainly from the institutes core funding from the fisheries ministry, i.e. the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries. Minor contribution from research grants.
Netherlands	<p>Mostly through NWO (Dutch Research Council) grants. Hence the project-based nature of the operation.</p> <p>Sometimes ships are chartered, but there is no data from this and it is also not useful for repeated sections of sorts.</p>
Poland	<p>IMWM-NRI: public funding - National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management</p> <p>IO PAN: Statutory activities supported with research grants.</p>
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Instituto Hidrografico/Portuguese Navy own budgets, for the missions that respond to national responsibilities, those that support the Portuguese Navy activity and others similar;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research grants, for the research projects in which IH is involved, do not pay directly shiptime but can support some mission costs such as consumables, the acquisition of some equipments, in some cases also human resources; • Clients, in case of contracts for conducting studies of environmental conditions.
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electra: Stockholm University and/or ship user • Skagerak: Ship user • Oden: Government • KBV 181: Umeå University for research; Governmental support for monitoring • Ocean Surveyor: Government • Svea: Government for monitoring

Country	How far in advance do you plan things
UK	<p>Research Cruises (NERC-funded): request for ship time goes in up to ~6 years in advance (at the proposal stage), and cruises start to be put into the program when funding is confirmed (>1 year in advance of the cruise, with some exceptions for repeat/long-term observations); program is published about 1 year out (though sometimes with uncertainties up to very short notice); the annual program is usually published in mid-summer for cruises starting in the following spring.</p> <p>Research Cruises (BAS): the Sir David Attenborough planning usually has a longer lead time (up to two years) and is planned around logistics required for BAS bases.</p> <p>SGMD: survey planning at very short notice, eg Nov-Dec for survey year Mar – Mar. But usually things are the same each year. All planning is year to year, by SLA agreement. Don't have 5 year or project funding.</p> <p>AFBINI: funding has been fairly consistent and sustained for last 20 yrs, but effort has increased in last ~5 yrs (doubling of stations measured per yr, more chemistry parameters added). New ship contract is signed, delivery due late 2026. There is pressure, ~ 10% cuts happening this yr.</p> <p>Cefas: year-to-year planning, eg Aug for following FY's cruises. Flexibility considered!</p>
Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 to 2 years for research shiptime applications • WFD programme follows a multi year cycle that covers the costs of vessel hire in estuaries and contracts the MI to cover coastal sites. • MSFD programme follows a multi year cycle . • CFP and EMFAF (previously called EMFF) programmes follows a multi year cycle .
Norway	In detail: a year ahead – but there are long term (5 yr) prioritizations
Italy	1 year (sometimes less when evaluation process is delayed); the plan is to have a biannual planning in the future
France	Coastal areas: at least 1 year ahead (once funded) High seas: at least 2 years ahead (once funded) A few observatories have a 5-year engagement but still have to submit a light proposal
Spain	Specific of every project.
Germany	Depending on the institutions and purpose of observations within: dedicated funding line for monitoring and hard wired into the long term budgets; short term research projects (DFG, BMBF, EU: typically 3 to 4 years); longer term and very broad research commitment (e.g. HGF programm oriented funding is now 6 years and funding is flexible to

	use; DAM Mission funding is 3 years with chance of renewal); ship applications run for a cruise and provide all support for observations to be carried out (no other project needed)
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • up to one year in advance as regarding the national plans • up to 4 years in case of EU research projects
Belgium	<p>RBINS: Cruise schedule is 1 year in advance</p> <p>VLIZ: Cruise schedule is 1 year in advance; Operational budget is negotiated every 5 years with Flemish Government</p> <p>MDK: Operational schedule is performed on short notice. Budget is fixed</p>
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annually, but in 6-year cycles, for the MFSD/WFD monitoring programmes • Over 3-4 year timeframes, for funded research projects • Annually, for fisheries monitoring programmes
Greece	Mostly 2-3 years for national funding, can be up to 6 years for European projects
Iceland	Cruise plan is decided on at the beginning of each year but ship time is foreseen approx. 3 years in advance or as long as the framework of the institutes financing.
Netherlands	6-18 months in advance.
Poland	<p>IMWM-NRI :</p> <p>Monitoring studies (their scope and frequency) are included in the monitoring programme and its updates are prepared in accordance with the requirements of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive every 6 years (last developed in 2018, next development in 2026)</p> <p>IOPAN:</p> <p>Statutory activities ensure the continuity of core research, so in the event of funding limitations, a reduction in the number of cruises is anticipated. However, there are no plans to discontinue operations entirely. Proposals and projects are typically planned year to year, with adjustments made based on the availability of resources.</p>
Portugal	<p>Operational Timeline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 year in advance the missions are inscribed in the operational planning of hydrographic ships. <p>Activity Timeline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Missions associated with national responsibilities can have a broad timeline, from regular character missions (planned at several years) to rapid response in case of emergencies (e.g. crisis at sea); • Missions associated with research projects typically confirmed after approval of the project (1-2 years after project proposal submission); final preparations starting 1 year in advance • Missions associated with contracts typically starting to be planned 1 year in advance but some shorter timelines also occur;
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electra: Very short-term planning. Only some courses and monitoring voyages are booked in advance • Skagerak: October for expeditions during the following year (i.e. 2 yrs advance) but open year-round for any schedule gaps • Oden: More than 2 yrs. Application for participation opens in February of the same year • KBV 181: October for expeditions during the upcoming year • Ocean Surveyor: Varies depending on project requirements • Svea: November for expeditions during the upcoming year

Country	Who decides about entering RIs
UK	Dept for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) has a RI team, who decide whether UK institutions may join an RI.
Ireland	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision is made by the RI consortium members 2. Structure important <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AISBL: decision at institute/company level (e.g. Marine Institute) • ERIC: need signoff by parent department (marine: DAFM). Discussions also held with the Irish National Contact Point and ESFRI delegate.
Norway	Ultimately Ministries, advices by research institutions Initiatives comes from scientists, lab directors
Italy	Ultimately Ministries, advices by research institutions Initiatives comes from scientists, lab directors
France	
Spain	?
Germany	<p>This depends on the type of RI:</p> <p>AISBL is via an institution and can be even via a PI that has a grant which allows to pay the membership fee (e.g. often this applies within EU projects but is very unlikely to be justifiable in national project such as DFG or BMBF).</p> <p>Other RIs e.g. ERIC – a structured process and maybe only HGF or larger cross-institutional interest groups can propose them. Convincing various actors of the need (one or better more heads of institutions, which in turn need to convince the respective ministry referat. Processes like applying for the ESFRI roadmap and alignment with the national RI roadmap are important. The national RI roadmap is a process supervised by the so called Wissenschaftsrat.</p> <p>The positive part: Once a RI is approved there is guarantee that the financing with specific ministry budget is maintained over the life-time of/membership in a RI</p>
Romania	The competent ministry has the final decision after consultation with the general Director(s)
Belgium	Initial request comes from the institute, who advocates the participation on the institute and country to the RI to regional and federal/national bodies. The latter (e.g. BELSPO, EWI, FWO, FNRS) will decide whether to join and how
Croatia	Normally (e.g., if being a part of an ERIC - European Research Infrastructure Consortium) it goes through a ministry dedicated to the science (currently Ministry of Science, Education and Youth), being the national coordinator, but in agreement with the research-performing organisations
Greece	Ministry makes the final decision about entering RIs following HCMR consultancy
Iceland	Initiative usually comes from senior scientist, decision is made at the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and the process is handled by Rannis, the Icelandic research council.

Netherlands	New RI's are decided by NWO (Dutch Research Council), the government and possibly the board of NWI.
Poland	<p>IMWM-NRI: Monitoring is carried out on the basis of an agreement between IMWM-NRI and the Chief Inspectorate for Environmental Protection, which coordinates the implementation of the State Environmental Monitoring. Both institutions decide on all activities and infrastructure</p> <p>IOPAN: Lab director.</p>
Portugal	<p>Entering RIs in the framework of national or European projects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1. Typically proposed by Instituto Hidrografico researchers from the Technical Direction of IH, following interactions with other institutes and research colleagues; • Step 2. Submitted to Heads of Divisions involved, followed by submission for approval to IH Technical Director • Step 3. Final aproval and ratification by the General Director of Instituto Hidrografico. <p>Entering RIs to be submitted to the ESFRI roadmap:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Steps 1 to 3 above; • Step 4. Interaction with the ESFRI National Delegation starts; • Step 5. Political support from Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education (through the ESFRI National Delegation) and from Ministry of National Defence; • Step 6. Proposal submitted at national level through the ESFRI National Delegation.
Sweden	The Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet; VR) is the funding body for national and international infrastructures. SWERVE is funded through the VR national infrastructure scheme, and any involvement of Sweden in an international research infrastructure would be funded through this same scheme.

7. Appendix Part 2. Slides from Introductory Webinars

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

EuroGOSHIP Pen Pictures
Richard Sanders & Kristin Richter, NORCE

Part of EuroGOSHIP Project led by Elaine McDonagh (NORCE)

December 2022 - November 2025

This work was funded by the European Union under grant agreement No. 101019742 (EuroGO-SHIP) and 101019743 (EuroGO-SHIP) under the EU government's Horizon Europe Funding programme (grant number: 101019742, 101019743). The content does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union or the European Commission. Source: https://www.eurogo-ship.eu/

1

Hydrography; one of the oldest ways of observing the ocean

- Shipboard observations
 - Top to bottom
 - Human Presence
 - (Virtually) unlimited power
 - High quality chemical analyses (pollutants, carbon system)
 - Calibration of remote assets
 - Model Initialisation
 - Change detection
- Undertaken by nearly every coastal state

Happy #CTDApocalypse! One of the workhorse technologies for physical and biogeochemical oceanography. Many CTD systems also allow to take up to 30 water samples at different depths. A colleague once mentioned that water is more valuable than gold when including all costs.

2

3

The challenge
Providing infrastructure that supports all European ship-based hydrography

Current issues & challenges:

- Certified reference materials
- Data
- Lack of agreed data and metadata formats for key data streams
- Diverse working practices
- Missed measurements
- Lack of national capacity for key measurements

The ICES Working Group on Oceanic Hydrography: A Bridge From In-situ Sampling to the Remote Autonomous Observation Era

Chair: Gordon Pirie*, Paula Fratton*, Agneta H. L. Larsen*, St. Peter Hubbert*, Graham Orr*, Adriaan Engelen*, Agneta H. L. Larsen*, Andrei Rostovtsev*, Alexander Tikhonov*, Kjetil Perren*, Roger Allen*, Boris Olin*, Alexander Koster*, Keesjan Luning*, Nicolas Kattner*, Paul Sarda*, Johannes Linderoth*, Tyler Woodcock*, Rose Strickland* and Caroline Coull*

4

EuroGO-SHIP
A European project funded by Horizon Europe

Consortium & resources

- 14 Partners, 11 nations
- 36 months (Dec 2022 – Nov 2025)
- Funding: €2,998,546
- EU and UKRI Funding

5

Our ambition
Could challenges be addressed by a new research infrastructure?

EU Marine Research Infrastructure Landscape
End Users: Scientific, Ocean modelling, Satellite community
Data handling: Copernicus Marine, EMODnet, SeaDataNet

EuroGO-SHIP: A new infrastructure for European ship-based hydrography

Adapted image from the ERCO Report 'The joint European Research Infrastructure Network for Coastal Observations, Assessment and Modelling for the Coast' published in 2013.

6

7

EuroGO-SHIP

EuroGOSHIP Pen Pictures: Part of WP4

What, Why, How

August 2024

8

- EuroGO-SHIP is exploring what a concept for a Research Infrastructure to support European Hydrography might look like:
- What services does the community need
 - Training?
 - Advocacy?
 - Standards?
 - Best Practices?
 - Data?
- If you have suggestions then please contact us

9

- As part of this we are compiling 'pen pictures' of what hydrography looks like in different countries
- 2-3 page, 10 slide overview of hydrography in countries
- Comparison and synthesis of pen pictures can give depth and context to main EuroGOSHIP results
- Important for EuroGOSHIP phase II
- Need to engage countries beyond International GOSHIP

10

- ### Pen Picture Questions
- Which organisations do Hydrography
 - Where, how often
 - What gets measured
 - Where does the data go
 - Why
 - Who Pays
 - How far in Advance are activities planned
 - Who decides about entering the RI?
 - Each country and group approaches this in their own way
 - Narrative, Pictures, Maps
 - Next slides are syntheses of results from individual countries, followed by some general

11

Where, how often

Fixed sections off the coast of Norway (upper figure) up to 6x a year, some only rarely
 Large ecosystem and fishery surveys (lower figure, excluding fixed sections) – usually once a year per region

What gets measured

Fixed sections: T, S, nutrients, zooplankton + oxygen, carbon chemistry
 Large ecosystem and fishery surveys – T, S

Where does the data go

Norwegian Marine Data Centre, ICES, MERCATOR etc

Why are they doing it

Watermass properties/distribution heat content, for ocean reanalyses, primary production status, ecosystem and fisheries status, OA monitoring, argo+ deployment and calibration

Who pays

Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (mostly) + Climate and Env. Ministry, Norwegian Research Council, EU projects

How far in advance do they plan things

In detail: a year ahead – but there are long term (5 yr) prioritizations

JUST ABOUT IEO ACTIVITIES

CSIC

What gets measured

Temperature and salinity alone?
Add in Oxygen, nutrients, carbon, CFCs etc
No tracers facility in Spain

MEDIAN IEO						
Country	IRAP/ICAN	IR/INMET	IR/ICAN	IR/ICAN	IR/ICAN	IR/ICAN
Spain	12	13	4	1	1	25
Italy	2	1	1	1	1	1
France	24	12	46	12	12	108
Greece						
Turkey						
Malta						
Cyprus						
Albania						
Bulgaria						
Romania						
Croatia						
Slovenia						
Montenegro						
North Macedonia						
Serbia						
Bosnia and Herzegovina						
Herzegovina						
Ukraine						
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